

Authorship in the Pauline Epistles: A stylometric and machine learning analysis

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Abstract

The authorship of the New Testament epistles, especially those attributed to Paul, is a crucial issue for both biblical scholarship and contemporary theology. Although previous quantitative studies have offered valuable insights, their “black box” nature has limited their interpretive value for theological and historical scholars. This study adopts a systematic, data-driven, and transparent framework combining computational stylometry with interpretable machine learning to re-evaluate the authorship of the Pauline corpus. The methodological pipeline includes Okapi BM25 weighting, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), hierarchical and k-means clustering, and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA). A conservative classification model, trained exclusively on the core letters, recognized them with high accuracy. Crucially, explainable AI (SHAP) identified the specific, lower-variance stylistic components that are decisive for this classification, providing transparent, replicable evidence for what constitutes a core “Pauline” style. The findings quantitatively demonstrate that the Deutero-Pauline and Pastoral Epistles are stylistically different from this core. This integrated approach

demonstrates how transparent data science can complement traditional exegesis, serving as a powerful bridge between quantitative analysis and historical theological inquiry.

Keywords: New Testament Greek; Stylometry; Okapi BM25; Principal Component Analysis (PCA); Random Forest; Hierarchical Clustering; Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA); SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations); Authorship Attribution

1. Introduction

1.1. The significance of authorship questions in the New Testament

The question of authorship—who wrote the 27 documents of the New Testament, when, and under what circumstances—is of paramount importance for developing a profound understanding of their historical, cultural, and theological contexts.¹ In particular, the authorship of the epistles attributed to the Apostle Paul, whose influence on the formation of early Christian thought was immense, has remained a central theme in biblical studies.² Among the 13 epistles traditionally ascribed to Paul, four, namely Romans, 1 & 2 Corinthians, and Galatians, are widely accepted as the “undisputed” or “core” Pauline epistles.³ In contrast, the authorship of Ephesians, Colossians, and 2 Thessalonians (the “Deutero-Pauline Epistles”), as well as 1 & 2 Timothy and Titus (the “Pastoral Epistles”), has been widely debated because of differences in vocabulary, style, and theological content.⁴ Further, although Hebrews was historically attributed to Paul, most modern scholars conclude it is not of Pauline authorship, because of its distinctive style.⁵ These classifications have been grounded primarily in traditional literary and historical critical methods.

¹ Guthrie, *New Testament Introduction*, p. 24; Metzger and Ehrman, *The Text of the New Testament*, p. 1.

² Dunn, *Theology of Paul the Apostle*, pp. 19–35; Sanders, *Paul: The Apostle’s Life, Letters, and Thought*, p. 1.

³ Mealand, “The extent of the Pauline corpus,” pp. 61–92; Greenwood, “St Paul Revisited—A Computational Result,” p. 43; Greenwood, “St Paul revisited—Word clusters in multidimensional space,” pp. 211–219.

⁴ Collins, *1 & 2 Timothy and Titus*, pp. 1–25; Johnson, *The First and Second Letters to Timothy*, p. 57; Mealand, “The extent of the Pauline corpus,” p. 62; Pracht and McCauley, “Paul’s style,” p. 2; Savoy, “Authorship of Pauline epistles revisited,” p. 1089; Towner, *The Letters to Timothy and Titus*, p. 2.

⁵ Attridge, *The Epistle to the Hebrews*, pp. 1–6; Koester, *Hebrews*, p. 2.

Determining whether specific epistles were genuinely written by Paul affects more than historical classification, as it shapes interpretations of doctrine, ecclesiastical authority, and pastoral instruction.⁶ Therefore, verifying authorship using transparent, data-driven criteria is not merely an academic exercise but a crucial endeavor for enriching theological and hermeneutical discourse.

1.2 Operational definition of “authorship”

In this study, “authorship” is treated as an operational label for the dominant stylistic profile of a text. It is acknowledged that ancient compositional practices included the use of amanuenses (secretaries), collaborative writing, and later editorial interventions. Therefore, the analysis does not presume solitary composition by a single individual. Rather, it tests whether a document exhibits a stable stylistic signal that aligns with or diverges from the profile learned from a conservative core of Pauline letters. The detected signals should be understood as products of the text’s compositional history, meaning the conclusions are probabilistic, focusing on stylistic proximity, rather than making definitive historical claims regarding a single author.

1.3. Development of stylometry and its application to New Testament studies

Stylometry proceeds from the hypothesis that authors possess a quantifiable “stylistic fingerprint” that is only partially under conscious control.⁷ Its origins can be traced back to the mid-19th century, but substantial progress followed the advent of computers.⁸ Morton⁹

⁶ Ehrman, *Forged: Writing in the Name of God*, pp. 23–45.

⁷ Holmes and Kardos, “Who was the author?,” pp. 5–8; Koppel et al., “Who was the author?,” pp. 9; Mosteller and Wallace, *Inference and Disputed Authorship*, p. 1.

⁸ De Morgan, “Letter to Rev. Heald,” pp. 215–216.

⁹ Morton, “The authorship of Greek prose,” pp. 169–233.

analyzed the Pauline epistles using statistical features such as sentence length and function word frequencies, laying the groundwork for subsequent research. Because function words are less dependent on topic, they are thought to reflect an author's unconscious habits and are therefore crucial in authorship analysis.¹⁰ Methodological research in stylometry has also progressed. Evert et al.¹¹ elucidated the mathematical principles of Burrows's delta measure, demonstrating that vector normalization plays a crucial role in enhancing authorship attribution performance. Their work demonstrated that for authorship identification, the overall deviation profile of high-frequency words matters more than any individual word, thereby strengthening the theoretical basis of stylometry.

Since Morton's original contributions, the field has moved from comparing isolated indicators to multivariate analyses that consider many linguistic features simultaneously.¹² This approach has enabled fine-grained explorations of the Pauline corpus,¹³ as well as comparative studies situating Paul within broader Greco-Roman literature.¹⁴ These approaches, along with the application of correspondence analysis by Erwin and Oakes¹⁵ and factor analysis by Baldwin,¹⁶ are part of a broader trend of applying multivariate analysis in humanities research.¹⁷ However, similar techniques have not always yielded consistent

¹⁰ Juola, "Authorship attribution," pp. 233–334; Kestemont, "ip attribution," pp. 59–100. pp. 59–100 et al., "Comp 59."

¹¹ Evert et al., "Understanding and explaining Delta measures," pp. ii4–ii16.

¹² Holmes, "The evolution of stylometry in humanities scholarship," pp. 111–117.

¹³ Greenwood, "St Paul Revisited—A Computational Result," pp. 43–47; Greenwood, "eSt Paul revisited—Word clusters in multidimensional space," pp. 211–216; Mealand, "The extent of the Pauline corpus," p. 61.

¹⁴ Luce and Robertson, "Comparing and assessing statistical distance metrics," 20240032.

¹⁵ Erwin and Oakes, "Correspondence Analysis of the New Testament," pp. 30–36.

¹⁶ Baldwin, "Factor analysis," pp. 7–25.

¹⁷ Kroonenberg, "Multivariate Humanities," pp. 143–159.

conclusions. For example, a recent study by Pracht and McCauley,¹⁸ using discrete probability models, reported no statistically significant stylistic difference between the undisputed Pauline epistles and the Pastoral Epistles, which is a finding at odds with the broad scholarly consensus. Therefore, ongoing debate concerns both the status of the Pastoral Epistles and robustness of competing quantitative methods, underscoring the need for approaches that enhance transparency and interpretability.

Recent research has progressed further with the introduction of machine learning.¹⁹ Models such as support vector machines, logistic regression, and random forests (an ensemble learning method)²⁰ can learn complex patterns from a large number of stylistic features and exhibit high predictive accuracy. Savoy²¹ analyzed the Pauline epistles by applying various distance measures such as Burrows's delta²² and Labbé's²³ cosine similarity, along with different validation protocols. Although these studies have shown that machine learning methods can achieve high accuracy for authorship attribution, they also highlight challenges such as difficulties with short texts, many candidate authors, and a lack of model interpretability.²⁴ A survey by Stamatatos²⁵ also provides a valuable overview of current

¹⁸ Pracht and McCauley, "Paul's style and the problem of the pastoral letters," 20240034.

¹⁹ Koppel, Schler, and Argamon, "Computational methods in authorship attribution," pp. 9–26; Savoy, *Machine Learning Methods for Stylometry*, p. 1; Stamatatos, "Methods for Stylometry on methods in authorship attribution," pp. 538; Zheng and Jin, "A review on authorship attribution in text mining," p. 1.

²⁰ Breiman, "Random forests," pp. 5–32.

²¹ Savoy, "Authorship of Pauline epistles revisited," pp. 1089–1097.

²² Burrows, "'Delta': A measure of stylistic difference," pp. 267–287.

²³ Labbé, "Experiments on authorship attribution by intertextual distance in English," pp. 33–80.

²⁴ Zheng and Jin, "A review on authorship attribution in text mining," e1584.

²⁵ Stamatatos, "A survey of modern authorship attribution methods," pp. 538–556.

authorship attribution methods. While powerful, these methods have often been criticized for their “black box” nature.

1.4 Clarifying the “Black Box” problem

In this context, a “black box” refers to a model that produces a classification (e.g., “Pauline” or “non-Pauline”) without revealing why it made that decision. This opacity limits its value for biblical scholars, as it is unclear which specific stylistic signals (e.g., vocabulary choices or phrase patterns) are driving the result. A central aim of this study is to overcome this limitation by using interpretable artificial intelligence (AI) to make model reasoning more transparent.

Despite recent advances, a significant research gap remains. Few studies have combined state-of-the-art text weighting (such as Okapi BM25), complementary dimensionality reduction stages, unsupervised exploration, and supervised, interpretable modeling that identifies which stylistic components drive classification across the entire New Testament corpus. Therefore, bridging the gap between predictive power and explanatory insight is the principal goal of this approach.

1.5. Uniqueness and objectives of this study

This study develops a robust, transparent, and reproducible framework for New Testament authorship analysis. The goal is to map the stylistic hierarchy within the Pauline corpus and its relationship to other New Testament documents, re-evaluating traditional authorship debates using modern computational tools.

This study addresses the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1: Do the 27 documents of the New Testament form statistically meaningful and recoverable stylistic clusters when analyzed using unsupervised learning methods?

- RQ2: Can a supervised machine learning model trained only on the undisputed Pauline epistles distinguish them from other documents with high accuracy? Further, which specific stylistic features drive this classification?
- RQ3: How are the Deutero-Pauline and Pastoral Epistles positioned stylistically relative to the core Pauline epistles? Do the quantitative results support or challenge the scholarly consensus?

By answering these questions, this study aims to move beyond simple attribution to provide a nuanced, multi-layered understanding of stylistic relationships, offering objective evidence that can inform and enrich theological and historical scholarship.

2. Methods

This study applied a range of computational stylometric techniques on the lemmatized word frequency data derived from the Greek source texts of the 27 New Testament books, aiming to analyze the authorship of the Pauline epistles. Each book was treated as a separate document. All analyses were conducted using Python 3.12 and major data science libraries, including pandas, NumPy, scikit-learn, SciPy, Matplotlib, seaborn, and Shapley additive explanations (SHAP).

2.1. Dataset construction and feature extraction

2.1.1. Baseline data

The textual data used in this study were drawn from a dataset published by The Center for New Testament Restoration.²⁶ This dataset is based on the Westcott and Hort²⁷ text,

²⁶ Robinson, *The Online Greek New Testament*.

²⁷ Westcott and Hort, *The New Testament in the Original Greek*, pp. v–xii.

integrating variant readings from the Nestle-Aland 27th edition (NA27),²⁸ and includes Strong's Numbers and morphological information for each word. To analyze authorial vocabulary choices independently of word inflection, this study used the 5,336 lemmas identified by Strong's Numbers as the unit of analysis.

2.1.2. Word weighting (Okapi BM25)

To evaluate the importance of each vocabulary item in each document, this study employed the Okapi BM25 algorithm, which is well recognized for its effectiveness in information retrieval.²⁹ BM25 reduces biases related to document topic and length, allowing for more detailed feature extraction. In a stylometric context, BM25 is particularly suitable because its sublinear term frequency saturation and document length normalization mitigate genre and length effects, while the inverse document frequency (IDF) component downweights ubiquitous function words, even after lemmatization, yielding more stable cross-document comparability in small-corpus settings such as the Greek New Testament. The BM25 score determines the relevance of a word q to a document D based on two key elements: IDF and normalized term frequency (TF). This calculation was directly implemented in Python using pandas and NumPy, following the mathematical model of Robertson and Walker.³⁰

First, the IDF for a word q , which indicates its rarity across the entire collection, was calculated using the following formula, which includes a smoothing term:

$$\text{IDF}(q) = \ln((N - n(q) + 0.5) / (n(q) + 0.5) + 1) \quad (1)$$

²⁸ Nestle and Aland, *Novum Testamentum Graece*, preface.

²⁹ Robertson and Walker, "Some simple effective approximations to the 2-Poisson model," pp. 232–241.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 235.

Here, N is the total number of documents (27), $n(q)$ is the number of documents in which word q appears, and \ln is the natural logarithm. The “+1” is a standard adjustment to ensure that the IDF does not become negative.

Next, the overall BM25 score is calculated as

$$\text{BM25}(q, D) = \text{IDF}(q) * [(f(q, D) * (k_1 + 1)) / (f(q, D) + k_1 * (1 - b + b * (|D| / \text{avgdl})))]$$

(2)

Here, $f(q, D)$ represents the frequency of word q in document D , $|D|$ is the total number of words in document D , and avgdl is the average document length across the entire collection. The benefit of BM25 compared with traditional TF-IDF (e.g., Salton and Buckley³¹) is its normalization parameters. k_1 adjusts term frequency saturation, while b controls the strength of document length normalization. This study adopted the standard recommended values of $k_1 = 1.2$ and $b = 0.75$.³² This procedure resulted in a $5,336 \times 27$ BM25 score matrix, which served as the foundational data for all subsequent multivariate analyses.

2.2. Dimensionality reduction

The BM25 score matrix is a high-dimensional dataset in which the number of features ($p = 5,336$) far exceeds the number of samples ($n = 27$). To build stable models from these p

³¹ Salton and Buckley, “Term-weighting approaches in automatic text retrieval,” pp. 513–523.

³² Robertson and Zaragoza, “The probabilistic relevance framework: BM25 and beyond,” pp. 333–389; Trotman, Puurula, and Burgess, “The probabilistic relevance framework: BM25 and beyond,” pp. 58–65.

>> n data, principal component analysis (PCA) was applied for dimensionality reduction and

to extract the essential stylistic structure.³³ Two complementary PCA approaches were used.

- Q-mode PCA (documents as observations): The stylistic proximity between documents was analyzed using a matrix of 27 documents (rows) by 5,336 words (columns). The resulting principal component scores, which represent each document's coordinates in the new reduced-dimensional space, were used to visualize overall relationships and as input features for later analyses.
- R-mode PCA (words as observations): The co-occurrence patterns among words were analyzed using a matrix of 5,336 words (rows) by 27 documents (columns). The principal component loadings from this analysis, which indicate each document's contribution to the formation of the principal component axes, were also used as feature vectors representing document style.

These two approaches were used in combination in a complementary manner. For both analyses, the top 10 principal components were extracted, balancing interpretability with cumulative explained variance.

2.3. Unsupervised learning for document grouping

To gain an exploratory understanding of the intrinsic structure among the documents, cluster analysis, which is an unsupervised learning method that does not require predefined

³³ Jolliffe and Cadima, "Principal component analysis: A review and recent developments," 20150202.

group labels, was conducted. Both hierarchical and non-hierarchical approaches were used to classify the documents into groups objectively, on the basis of their similarity. The use of BM25 as a feature weighting scheme has been demonstrated to be effective for such document clustering tasks.³⁴

2.3.1. Hierarchical clustering

To clarify hierarchical relationships based on stylistic similarity, dendrograms were generated. Two key methods were used on each of three different datasets (BM25 scores, Q-mode PCA scores, and R-mode PCA loadings) to evaluate robustness.

- **L2-normalized Euclidean distance and Ward’s method:** After L2-normalizing each data vector (scaling the vector length to one), the Euclidean distance was calculated, and clusters were merged using Ward’s method,³⁵ which minimizes the within-cluster variance. This combination promotes the formation of compact, spherical clusters while considering the “pattern” of vocabulary use.
- **Cosine distance and the average linkage method:** Using cosine distance, which directly measures the angle between documents, clusters were merged using the average linkage method, enabling more flexible cluster formation.

2.3.2. Non-hierarchical clustering (k-means)

The k-means method, which groups documents into a set number of clusters (k), was used on the principal component representations from both Q-mode (scores) and R-mode (loadings) analyses. The best number of clusters (k) was initially estimated for each dataset

³⁴ Whissell and Clarke, “Improving Document Clustering Using Okapi BM25 Feature Weighting,” pp. 2421–2424.

³⁵ Ward Jr, “Hierarchical grouping to optimize an objective function,” pp. 236–244.

using the elbow method, and then the classification results for $k = 3$ to $k = 8$ were compared and examined.

2.4. Supervised learning for authorship model construction and validation

To develop a hypothesis-testing model for Pauline authorship, a “ground truth” was established by using a deliberately conservative and methodologically rigorous approach. Only the four undisputed major epistles (Romans, 1 & 2 Corinthians, Galatians) were identified as “authentically Pauline (class 1),” and all 23 other documents as “non-Pauline (class 0).” This methodological choice is based on the broad scholarly consensus that these four letters form the most stylistically consistent and reliable core of the Pauline corpus.³⁶

The reason for this strict definition is to create the most rigorous test possible for “Pauline-ness.” By training the model solely on this undisputed core, the analysis aims to capture the clearest and purest stylistic signal of Paul’s writing. Including other letters, even those with strong claims to authenticity, such as Philippians or 1 Thessalonians, could introduce stylistic variance related to different topics, audiences, or writing conditions, thereby “polluting” the signal and weakening the model’s ability to discriminate. This approach allows for asking a specific question: how closely do other texts match the stylistic standard set by the most confidently attributed works of Paul?

- **Models:** Two types of models were applied, namely logistic regression and random forest,³⁷ the latter of which can capture more complex nonlinear relationships.
- **Performance evaluation and model robustness validation:** To assess the generalization performance of the models objectively, repeated stratified k-fold cross-

³⁶ Mealand, “Hierarchical grouping”.g to optimize an o 61–92.

³⁷ Breiman, “Hierarchical grouping”. 5–32.

validation was performed (4 folds, 30 repetitions), resulting in 120 training and evaluation cycles, providing a highly stable estimate of model accuracy.

- **Optimal feature selection:** Recursive feature elimination with cross-validation was employed to identify the combination of principal components that maximizes model performance for both Q-mode and R-mode feature sets.

2.5. Discriminant analysis (LDA)

To evaluate how well predefined authorial and genre groups can be stylistically distinguished, LDA was conducted. Using three datasets, namely raw BM25 scores, Q-mode PCA scores, and R-mode PCA loadings, as explanatory variables, discriminant functions were derived and visualized to examine the degree of group separation.

2.6. Model interpretability (SHAP)

To elucidate the rationale behind the random forest model's classification results, SHAP was applied to models trained on both Q-mode PCA scores and R-mode PCA loadings,³⁸ enabling the visualization of both the direction and magnitude of each principal component's contribution to the predicted probability for each document, offering insights into the specific decision-making process in each model.

2.7. Methodological rationale and analytical workflow

The multi-stage analytical pipeline adopted in this study was designed to progress from data representation and exploratory analysis to hypothesis testing and model interpretation. Each step builds upon the previous step to ensure a comprehensive and robust investigation.

³⁸ Lundberg and Lee, "A unified approach to interpreting model predictions," pp. 4765–4774.

(1) Text vectorization (BM25): The initial step was to convert the raw Greek texts into a quantitative format. Okapi BM25 was selected over simpler methods such as TF-IDF based on its better handling of document length normalization, which is essential when comparing texts of different sizes, from the Gospel of Luke to the Epistle to Philemon.

(2) Dimensionality reduction and structure extraction (PCA): The resulting BM25 matrix was high dimensional and noisy. PCA was applied to reduce this noise and extract the most significant axes of stylistic variation. Both Q-mode (analyzing documents) and R-mode (analyzing words) PCA were employed to gain complementary perspectives, where Q-mode provides a “map” of how documents relate to each other, and R-mode reveals the shared vocabulary patterns that define the underlying stylistic dimensions.

(3) Exploratory Analysis (Clustering): Before forming any scholarly hypotheses, unsupervised clustering (hierarchical and k-means) was first applied to the PCA-reduced data. This exploratory step helped identify natural, data-driven groupings among the documents, offering an objective, hypothesis-generating perspective of the corpus structure.

(4) Hypothesis testing (supervised learning & LDA): The subsequent supervised analyses tested specific, long-standing scholarly hypotheses.

- The **random forest and logistic regression models** were designed to test the binary hypothesis of Pauline authorship, using the strict “core four” epistles as the ground truth (as justified in Section 2.4). This approach provides a probabilistic measure of how “Pauline” each document is.
- **LDA** served a complementary purpose. Instead of a binary classification, LDA tested the statistical separability of predefined multi-class groups based on

scholarly consensus (e.g., Core Pauline, Pastorals, Johannine, Narrative). This approach confirms the coherence of these traditional categories within the stylistic space outlined by PCA.

(5) Model interpretation (SHAP): Finally, to ensure transparency and go beyond “black box” predictions, SHAP analysis was conducted on the best-performing random forest model. This final step elucidates why the model made its classifications by identifying which specific principal components (i.e., which underlying stylistic features) were most influential in each document. This approach links the quantitative results to an understandable analytical narrative.

This integrated workflow ensures that the conclusions are not based on a single method but are triangulated across exploratory, hypothesis-testing, and interpretive approaches.

3. Results

The multi-stage stylometric methods used in this study produced consistent and multi-layered results regarding the stylistic relationships among the 27 New Testament documents. This section first presents the characteristic words of each document as identified by BM25 scores, followed by the visualization of the overall structure through PCA, results of exploratory cluster analysis, quantitative assessment of authorship using supervised learning models, verification of group separation through discriminant analysis, and explanation of the model’s rationale using SHAP.

3.1. Characteristic words in each document from BM25 scores

To evaluate how well the foundational BM25 scores reflect the thematic and stylistic features of each document, the top 10 words with the highest scores in each document were

extracted (Table 1). The results reveal that BM25 accurately identifies the characteristic words of each text. For example, in the Gospel of Matthew, “τάλαντον” (talanton, G5007), in Mark, “ἐκθαμβέω” (to be greatly amazed, G1568), and in the Epistle to the Hebrews, “Μελχισεδέκ” (Melchizedek, G3198), which are words central to the narrative or theology of each respective document, appeared at the top. Further, in 1 Timothy, a Pastoral Epistle, “ἀνεπίληπτος” (above reproach, G423), which indicates the quality of a leader, ranked highly, reflecting the document’s theme. This pattern demonstrates that BM25 is an effective weighting method for capturing a document’s uniqueness in theme and style, not simply word frequency, thereby supporting the reliability of the subsequent multivariate analyses.

3.2. Extraction of stylistic structure via PCA

To extract the essential stylistic structure from the BM25 score matrix, PCA was performed using both Q-mode (documents as observations) and R-mode (words as observations) approaches.

3.2.1. Q-mode analysis: Stylistic positioning of documents

First, to visualize the overall stylistic relationships between documents, a Q-mode analysis was conducted. Figure 1 presents the 27 documents in a 2D space based on their scores on the top two principal components (PC1, PC2). This “stylistic map” immediately reveals that the documents are not randomly distributed but have a clear structure. PC1, the horizontal axis, distinctly separates the narrative books (positive scores) from the epistles (negative scores), indicating a major genre divide.

However, a closer look reveals additional nuance. While Luke, Matthew, and Mark seem to be grouped in the upper-right quadrant of the stylistic map, Acts is positioned in the lower-right quadrant, separated from the Synoptic Gospels by its strongly negative score on

PC2. This distance reflects a broader narrative genre affinity (shown by PC1) but also notable internal stylistic differences within this group (shown by PC2), aligning with the detailed component scores presented in Table 2.

The top 10 principal components extracted from this Q-mode analysis explained 68.9% of the total variance in the data (Table 2). Each principal component acts as a coordinate axis that positions the 27 New Testament documents based on specific stylistic features. A detailed examination of the principal component scores in Table 2 further clarifies the structure shown in Figure 1.

- **PC1 (16.0% of variance)** is the most powerful axis separating the narrative books from the epistles. Acts (score: 114.2), Luke (63.5), and Matthew (39.1) have large positive scores, whereas most of the epistles have negative scores.
- **PC2 (12.0% of variance)** functions as an axis that separates the narrative books internally. Synoptic Gospels such as Luke (74.2), Matthew (53.1), and Mark (37.6) are positioned in the positive direction, while Acts exhibits a large negative score of -82.3, resulting in clear separation.
- **PC4 (6.4% of variance)** can be described as the “Hebrews axis,” capturing the outstanding uniqueness of the Epistle to the Hebrews (89.5). While the scores of all other documents fall within the range of -11.2 to 18.8, only Hebrews exhibits an anomalous value, strongly suggesting that its style is different from that of any other document.

The specific vocabulary differences reflected by these principal components can be clarified by examining the word loadings for each component (Table 3). For example, on PC4, which indicates the uniqueness of Hebrews, theological terms specific to that document, such as “Μελχισεδέκ” (Melchizedek, G3198), “τράγος” (goat, G5131), and “δεκάτη” (a tenth,

G1181), have particularly high loadings, confirming that this axis captures themes unique to Hebrews, such as the priesthood and atonement.

3.2.2. R-mode analysis: Document groups defining stylistic axes and their constituent vocabulary

To verify the observed structure from another angle, an R-mode analysis was conducted. This method identifies stylistic axes from word co-occurrence patterns and computes the principal component loadings, which reveal how much each document contributes to the formation of these axes (Table 4). This loading matrix is a key insight of this study, demonstrating that biblically meaningful document groups exist as objective statistical axes. For example, PC1 can be interpreted as the “narrative style” axis, as the Gospels have large positive loadings; PC2 is the “Pauline epistolary style” axis, with the Pauline epistles having positive loadings; and PC6 is the axis that clearly separates the Pastoral Epistles (positive) from the Johannine epistles (negative). Further, PC5 is an axis that highlights the strong homogeneity of Ephesians and Colossians, as these are the only two documents with exceptionally high positive loadings.

The word groups that characterize each principal component extracted in the R-mode analysis were identified by their principal component scores (Table 5). For example, for PC1, which defines the style of the Gospels, words with high positive scores, such as μαθητής (disciple, G3101), ὄχλος (crowd, G3793), and Φαρισαῖος (Pharisee, G5330), are listed, confirming that it reflects a narrative context.

By combining Q-mode and R-mode analyses with interpretations at both the document and word levels, the multi-layered stylistic structure of the New Testament documents is uncovered. This detailed structural understanding forms the foundation for interpreting the subsequent clustering and discriminant analyses.

3.3. Exploration of document groups via hierarchical clustering

To examine the stylistic similarities between documents from various perspectives, hierarchical clustering was conducted on three different datasets (BM25 scores, Q-mode PCA scores, and R-mode PCA loadings) using two representative methods. The first method was the “L2-normalized Euclidean distance + Ward’s method” (Figures 2(a)–(c)), which promotes the formation of compact, spherical clusters. The second was the “cosine distance + average linkage method” (Figures 3(a)–(c)), which allows for more flexible clustering.

When examining the results of Ward’s method (Figures 2(a)–(c)), it is clear that preprocessing with PCA significantly contributes to clarifying the structure. Even with the raw BM25 data (Figure 2(a)), there is a tendency for the narrative books and Pauline epistles to group together; however, the clusters are complex and intertwined. In contrast, reducing dimensionality with PCA makes the structure much clearer. Specifically, the model using the R-mode PCA loadings (Figure 2(c)) provides the most understandable results, closely aligning with biblical scholarship. In this dendrogram, the 27 New Testament documents are distinctly divided into meaningful groups as follows:

- At the largest branch, the documents are first broadly divided into a “Gospel cluster” (orange branch) and a wide range of other documents.
- Within the Gospel cluster, the Gospel of John (04 JOH) first branches off, indicating its uniqueness, after which Luke (03 LU), Matthew (01 MT), and Mark (02 MR) join at a very low distance, forming a solid “Synoptic Gospels” group.
- In the other major branch, the Pauline epistles are divided into three hierarchical sub-clusters that correspond with traditional classifications.

- **Core Pauline cluster (green branch):** The four major epistles (Romans, 1 & 2 Corinthians, Galatians) and Philippians (11 PHP) form a very tight group.
- **Deutero-Pauline cluster (purple branch):** Ephesians (10 EPH) and Colossians (12 COL) form a distinct pair.
- **Pastoral cluster (red branch):** 1 & 2 Timothy and Titus (15, 16, 17) form their own solid cluster, completely separate from all other Pauline-related epistles.
- Among other documents, Acts (05 AC) often clusters with stylistically unique documents such as Hebrews (19 HEB) and Revelation (27 RE), in a location completely different from the Gospel of Luke, who is its attributed author.

Next, the results of the average linkage method (Figures 3(a)–(c)) were examined. This approach, while indicating a similar overall structure compared with Ward’s method, offers more flexible clustering and helps verify the robustness of the findings. When examining the model using R-mode PCA loadings (Figure 3(c)), the core groups confirmed by Ward’s method (Figure 2(c)), namely, the “Synoptic Gospels,” “Pastoral Epistles,” and “Ephesians–Colossians pair,” are maintained as very strong clusters. Conversely, the cohesion of the core Pauline epistles appears looser, with chain-like connections to other epistles, reflecting the characteristics of the average linkage method.

These comparative analyses strongly indicate that the major document groups identified in this study (Synoptic Gospels, core Pauline epistles, Deutero-Pauline epistles, Pastoral Epistles, etc.) are robust structures inherent in the data, consistently appearing even when different clustering methods are used. The model combining R-mode PCA loadings

with Ward's method (Figure 2(c)) provides the clearest visualization of the hierarchical structure of the New Testament documents.

3.4. Non-hierarchical clustering (k-means) for group classification

In the k-means analysis, the elbow method plots (Figures 4(a) and 4(b)) indicate that $k = 2$ or $k = 3$ is the optimal number of clusters for the R-mode data, whereas the Q-mode plot is nearly linear, suggesting no single optimum. To explore the finer substructures, the results for $k = 3$ to $k = 8$ for both datasets (Tables 6(a) and 6(b)) were examined.

The R-mode PCA loadings (Table 6(b)) yielded a particularly clear and interpretable separation. As the value of k increased, the major groups observed in the hierarchical clustering were sequentially separated.

- **For $k = 5$:** The Pastoral Epistles (1 & 2 Timothy, Titus) separated from the diverse documents cluster to form their own cluster (Cluster 4). At this point, the three main tiers of the Pauline epistles (core, Deutero-Pauline, and Pastoral) were clearly separated into different clusters.
- **For $k = 6$:** Galatians (09 GA) rejoined the core Pauline cluster (Cluster 0), while the three Johannine epistles (23 1JO, 24 2JO, 25 3JO) separated to form their own distinct cluster (Cluster 2).
- **For $k = 8$:** Several key realignments occurred. Revelation (27 RE) separated from Hebrews to rejoin the Gospel cluster (now Cluster 1), which was also joined by Acts (05 AC). Concurrently, 1 & 2 Thessalonians broke away from the main Pauline group to form their own distinct cluster (Cluster 0). Throughout this process, the Pastoral Epistles (Cluster 4) and group of Ephesians, Colossians, and Philemon (Cluster 5) maintained their own stable clusters.

The k-means method using R-mode PCA loadings clearly demonstrates that, as the value of k increases, the major groups observed in hierarchical clustering are progressively separated into meaningful units. This trend strongly supports the conclusion that the document groups identified in this study are stable structures inherent in the data, regardless of any specific analysis.

3.5. Quantitative evaluation of authorship via supervised learning

Using a ground truth in which the four major epistles were labeled as “authentically Pauline (class 1)” and all others were labeled as “non-Pauline (class 0),” logistic regression and random forest classification models were constructed. Analysis was conducted on three different datasets, namely (1) raw BM25 data, (2) Q-mode PCA scores, and (3) R-mode PCA loadings, and the resulting performances were compared.

- **Model performance:**

- Table 7 presents the performance evaluations for the different combinations of three datasets and two algorithms. The average accuracy from repeated stratified k-fold cross-validation (30 trials) indicates that preprocessing with PCA significantly enhances model performance.
- The best performance was achieved by the random forest model using Q-mode PCA scores, with an average accuracy of 96.2% (standard deviation 0.066). The confusion matrix for this model, which is based on a single stratified four-fold cross-validation, was [TN=23, FP=0, FN=1, TP=3], indicating that it did not misclassify any non-Pauline documents and misclassified only one of the four authentic Pauline epistles.

- When using R-mode PCA loadings, the logistic regression model achieved 95.9% accuracy and the random forest model achieved 92.2% accuracy, both demonstrating similarly high precision.
- In contrast, when using the raw BM25 data, the accuracy for both the random forest and logistic regression was only 85.1%, clearly illustrating the effectiveness of dimensionality reduction and feature extraction through PCA.
- **Prediction probabilities:**
 - When examining the prediction probabilities from the top-performing random forest model using Q-mode PCA scores (Table 8), the four main epistles exhibited high probability values (0.61 or higher), while the other 23 documents all had very low probabilities (0.19 or lower). This pattern indicates that even traditionally authentic epistles such as Philippians and 1 Thessalonians were considered to deviate from the strict stylistic model established by the four major epistles. A similar trend was observed in the model using R-mode PCA loadings, which consistently exhibited a clear stylistic gap between the four major epistles and other documents across both datasets.
- **Feature importance:**
 - An analysis of the features emphasized by the random forest model revealed that for the model using Q-mode PCA scores, PC5 (0.278), PC6 (0.250), and PC7 (0.128) were the most important, whereas for the model using R-mode PCA loadings, PC2 (0.269), PC3 (0.153), and PC6 (0.124) were identified as the most important (Table 9).

3.6. Verification of group separation via discriminant analysis (LDA)

To verify how clearly predefined authorial/genre groups could be separated stylistically, LDA was performed. For this analysis, the 27 documents were categorized into six predefined groups based on long-standing scholarly consensus regarding genre and authorship traditions:³⁹ (1) Core Pauline Epistles (Romans, 1-2 Corinthians, Galatians), (2) Deutero-Pauline Epistles (Ephesians, Colossians, 2 Thessalonians), (3) Pastoral Epistles (1-2 Timothy, Titus), (4) Narrative Books (Gospels and Acts), (5) Johannine Literature (Gospel of John, 1-3 John, Revelation), and (6) Hebrews as a unique category. The purpose of LDA is to determine the statistical separability of these traditional groupings using the stylometric features. This analysis used three types of datasets as explanatory variables, namely (1) raw BM25 data, (2) Q-mode PCA scores, and (3) R-mode PCA loadings, and the results were compared.

3.6.1. Discriminant analysis on raw BM25 data

First, when using the 5,336-dimensional raw BM25 scores directly, as shown in Figure 5, the linguistic uniqueness of the Epistle to the Hebrews overshadowed all other differences between the documents. The primary discriminant axis (LD1) essentially became a measure of “Hebrews-ness,” with all other documents being grouped near the origin, making it difficult to observe their internal structure. This outcome emphasizes the importance of preprocessing with PCA to extract a more fundamental stylistic structure.

3.6.2. Group separation based on PCA data

When using the dimensionally reduced datasets from the PCA, the discriminant analysis yielded extremely clear results. When using either the 10 principal component scores

³⁹ Guthrie, *New Testament Introduction*, pp. 529–550; Metzger and Ehrman, *The Text of the New Testament*, p. 1.

from Q-mode analysis (Figure 6) or the R-mode PCA loadings (Figure 7) as explanatory variables, the predefined groups formed clearly separated clusters.

The model using Q-mode scores correctly classified all 27 documents into their predefined groups, achieving 100% classification accuracy, indicating that the defined grouping is statistically perfectly separable in the PCA-extracted stylistic space.

3.6.3. Interpretation of discriminant axes

Model separation performance can also be assessed according to how much of the between-group variance the discriminant axes can explain. As shown in Table 10, in the model using Q-mode scores, the first two discriminant axes, LD1 and LD2, can explain 99.3% of the total between-group variance (71.8% and 27.5%, respectively). The R-mode model was also highly effective, with its first two axes explaining 88.6% of the variance. The specific scores of each document on these discriminant axes are detailed in Table 11.

When examining the plot based on these scores (Figure 6), it is clear that LD1 acts as an axis dividing major genres such as “narrative books” (right side of the plot), “epistles” (center), and “Hebrews” (far left). This separation on LD1 is also evident in the group-wise score distributions presented in Figure 8(a). Conversely, LD2 serves as an axis differentiating epistles internally, strongly distinguishing the Pastoral Epistles (top of the plot) from the other epistles. The R-mode model’s first discriminant axis (Figure 8(b)) exhibits a similar but less distinct separation, with the Pastoral Epistles in a separate negative space while other groups cluster closer to zero.

To understand which stylistic features these discriminant axes represent, the loadings (coefficients) of each principal component on the discriminant functions were analyzed (Table 12, Figure 9). For the Q-mode model (Figure 9(a)), the results revealed that LD1, which separates genres, was influenced mainly by the large negative coefficient of PC4

(-16.9), with PC1 (5.05) and PC5 (4.61) also playing a role. Conversely, LD2, which distinguishes the epistles internally, was primarily driven by the extremely large negative coefficient of PC1 (-9.28), with contributions from PC2 (-3.97), PC3 (-2.10), and, in the positive direction, PC6 (2.37). The R-mode loadings plot (Figure 9(b)) reveals a different pattern, where LD1 is shaped by a contrast between PC3 (negative) and PC1/PC6 (positive), whereas LD2 is mostly defined by the opposition between PC1 (negative) and PC2/PC6 (positive). The fact that PC6 is influential in both Q-mode and R-mode analyses highlights its significance in terms of defining stylistic differences among the epistles.

3.7. Elucidation of model rationale (SHAP Analysis)

Finally, to elucidate “why” the random forest models produced their specific classification results, SHAP analysis was applied to the models trained on both Q-mode and R-mode data.

- **Identification of important features:** The results of recursive feature elimination (RFE) (Figures 10(a) and 10(b)) indicated that only a small subset of principal components was sufficient to maximize model performance in both cases. The SHAP summary plots (Figures 11(a) and 11(b)) visually confirm which components contributed most significantly to the classification. For the Q-mode model (Figure 11(a)), PC6, PC5, and PC4 were the main drivers. For the R-mode model (Figure 11(b)), PC2, PC3, and PC6 were the most influential.
- **Rationale for individual document predictions:** The individual force plots (Figure 12) illustrate how the prediction probability for each document was calculated. To interpret these plots, begin from the “base value” (the gray vertical line), which represents the average prediction across all documents (a prior probability of 0.15 that any random document is Pauline). Features (principal components) then act as

“forces” pushing the prediction higher (in red, indicating Pauline-like features) or lower (in blue, indicating non-Pauline-like features). The final predicted probability is the sum of the base value and all feature contributions.

For example, in the Q-mode analysis of Hebrews (Figure 12(a)), the model’s reasoning becomes transparent. PC4 (the “Hebrews axis”) and PC7 provide a slight push toward a “Pauline” classification (red arrows), reflecting some shared theological vocabulary. However, this effect is overwhelmingly counteracted by the strong negative influence of PC6 and PC5 (large blue arrows), which represent stylistic patterns highly uncharacteristic of the core Pauline epistles. The final prediction results from the sum of these competing forces, leading to a clear “non-Pauline” classification. The case of 1 Timothy (Figure 12(e)) is even more straightforward. Here, nearly all influential principal components act as blue arrows, pushing the prediction lower. The model detects almost no stylistic features it recognizes as Pauline, offering a clear and understandable rationale for its classification. The R-mode force plots (Figures 12(f) to 12(j)) provide an additional perspective, often highlighting different principal components but still resulting in the same overall classification, which supports the robustness of the findings.

These results demonstrate that the models constructed in this study not only classify with high accuracy but also provide their rationale at the principal component level for both Q-mode and R-mode analytical frameworks.

4. Discussion

This study systematically integrated Okapi BM25 word weighting, dual-mode PCA (Q-mode and R-mode), multiple clustering techniques, supervised machine learning models, and discriminant analysis to conduct a comprehensive investigation of the authorship and

stylistic connections among the 27 New Testament texts, especially the Pauline epistles. As a final step, SHAP analysis was employed to clarify the reasoning behind the model's decisions. The findings offer new quantitative evidence for longstanding debates in biblical scholarship and also propose methodological advances for the field of stylometry.

4.1. Overall stylistic structure: A map of the New Testament by multivariate analysis

The PCA and clustering analyses revealed that the 27 New Testament documents are not merely a random collection of styles but instead possess a clear and robust structure. Specifically, the Q-mode PCA, which examined the relationships among documents, revealed that the top 10 principal components account for 68.9% of the total variance, confirming that the high-dimensional vocabulary data can be effectively condensed. The scatter plot illustrating these principal component scores (Figure 1) offers a visual “map” of the documents, indicating the presence of clusters based on major genres such as narrative books (Gospels and Acts) and the broader group of epistles. This finding is consistent with multivariate analysis results reported by Greenwood⁴⁰ and Mealand.⁴¹

Further, this study used hierarchical clustering with multiple datasets and distance measures as an exploratory method. The results revealed that, although rough groupings were visible even with raw BM25 data, using PCA-reduced data (Q-mode PCA scores or R-mode PCA loadings) produced more interpretable clusters that closely match existing theological scholarship, likely because PCA helped remove noise from document-specific topics and vocabulary, extracting a more essential, authorship-related stylistic structure.

⁴⁰ Greenwood, “St. Paul revisited: A computational result,” pp. 43–47; Greenwood, “St. Paul revisited: Word clusters,” pp. 211–219.

⁴¹ Mealand, “The extent of the Pauline corpus,” pp. 61–92.

The model combining L2-normalized Euclidean distance and Ward's method based on R-mode PCA loadings clearly separated the documents into distinct clusters (Figure 2(c)). In this dendrogram, Hebrews first diverges significantly from all other documents, highlighting its uniqueness. Then, the documents are broadly divided into "narrative books" and a wide range of "epistles." Within the epistles, the documents in the Pauline tradition form a clear hierarchical structure: (1) the "core Pauline epistles," consisting of the four major epistles and Philippians; (2) "Deutero-Pauline epistles," consisting of Ephesians and Colossians; and (3) "Pastoral Epistles," which are entirely separate from all other Pauline-related epistles. The effectiveness of L2-normalized distance, which is less influenced by document length or overall vocabulary usage, supports the fundamental hypothesis of stylometry that an author's style is reflected in the "patterns" and "proportions" of vocabulary choice.

The k-means non-hierarchical clustering demonstrated the complementary strengths of the Q-mode and R-mode approaches. The R-mode loadings (Table 6(b)) produced a clear, sequential separation of the major groups, confirming their stability. However, the Q-mode scores (Table 6(a)) resulted in less distinct clusters. This result indicates that R-mode loadings, which measure each document's contribution to shared stylistic axes, are more appropriate for partitioning, whereas Q-mode scores are better for visualizing overall distances and separations.

LDA confirmed this structural validity objectively. The six predefined author/genre groups were perfectly separated with 100% accuracy using Q-mode PCA scores as features (Figure 6). The first discriminant axis (LD1) explained 71.8% of the total variance, mainly distinguishing genres such as "narrative books," "epistles," and "Hebrews," while the second discriminant axis (LD2) accounted for the remaining 27.5%, effectively differentiating the gradations of "Pauline-ness" within the epistles (Table 10). The consistency of these results across various analytical methods strongly supports the robustness of the recovered structure.

4.1.1 Methodological rationale and complementarity

Okapi BM25 was chosen because it balances term frequency with document length and corpus-wide rarity, which is crucial for unevenly sized Koine Greek documents. Q-mode PCA summarizes inter-document distances, whereas R-mode PCA identifies latent stylistic axes defined by co-occurring lexemes. Together, they provide document-level mapping and word-level interpretation. Hierarchical and k-means clustering offer convergent exploratory validation of grouping structure; LDA tests the statistical separability of theoretically posited groups; and supervised models (logistic regression, random forest) quantify authorship probabilities. Finally, SHAP provides model transparency by attributing predictions to specific components. These techniques were preferred over alternatives (e.g., Burrows's delta, topic models, or purely function-word methods) because they provide simultaneous genre control, component-level interpretability, and robustness on small corpora.

4.2. The hierarchy of the Pauline corpus: A quantitative evaluation by probabilistic models

The analysis of the Pauline corpus, which was the main focus of this study, quantitatively demonstrated the existence of a clear hierarchical structure within it through the application of supervised learning models. Both logistic regression and random forest models, especially the random forest model using Q-mode PCA scores (cross-validation accuracy 96.2%, Table 7), revealed a noticeable stylistic gap between the four major epistles (Romans, 1 & 2 Corinthians, Galatians) and the other documents.

The prediction probabilities results were remarkable. The four major epistles received high probability values (≥ 0.61), while the other 23 documents all had very low probabilities (≤ 0.19) (Table 8). This pattern indicates that even traditionally authentic epistles such as

Philippians and 1 Thessalonians were assessed to deviate from the strict stylistic model established by the four major epistles. This outcome aligns perfectly with the structure observed in hierarchical clustering (Figure 2(c)). In other words, the four major epistles form the most coherent core, with Philippians and the Thessalonian letters nearby, followed by the Deutero-Pauline epistles (Ephesians, Colossians) further out, and the Pastoral Epistles lying in a completely separate domain. This concentric hierarchical structure was confirmed by supervised learning.

This finding prompts important theoretical questions regarding what “stylistic proximity” actually means. In this study, stylistic homogeneity, as measured by the computational model, acted as a proxy for a steady authorial signal. Although it does not definitively establish single authorship, a high degree of stylistic distance such as that observed in the Pastoral Epistles strongly challenges the hypothesis of direct Pauline authorship under normal circumstances. This nuance of “similarity yet non-identity” for letters such as Philippians suggests that their writing contexts, including differences in topic, emotional tone, or the degree of secretarial involvement, may have varied from those of the four major epistles. It is important to recognize that ancient letter-writing practices, including the use of amanuenses (secretaries), could introduce stylistic variations.⁴² Although the model cannot distinguish between a different author and significant secretarial influence, it objectively measures the level of stylistic deviation from Paul’s core practice, offering a data-driven basis for such historical and theological debates.

The extremely low prediction probabilities for the Deutero-Pauline epistles (Ephesians, Colossians, 2 Thessalonians) indicate that, in addition to the literary dependence between Ephesians and Colossians highlighted by Mitton⁴³ and Coutts,⁴⁴ both epistles are

⁴² Richards, *The Secretary in the Letters of Paul*, pp. 19–45.

⁴³ Mitton, *The Epistle to the Ephesians*, pp. 68–75.

stylistically distant from the core Pauline style. This finding is consistent with the scholarly hypothesis of a “Pauline school” that developed his thought under his name.

Further, the fact that the Pastoral Epistles (1 & 2 Timothy, Titus) received probabilities as low as, or even lower than, other non-Pauline documents provides strong statistical evidence of their non-Pauline character. This result reaffirms the “non-Pauline nature of the Pastoral Epistles,” which has been consistently highlighted by stylometry from the early research of Grayston and Herdan⁴⁵ to the recent studies by Mealand⁴⁶ and Savoy,⁴⁷ using the latest machine learning models.

4.3. Elucidating the model’s rationale: What SHAP analysis revealed about “Pauline-ness”

One of the major contributions of this study is that it “opened the black box” of the machine learning models by using SHAP analysis to visualize their reasoning. RFE identified that only three features were required to optimize the model’s performance using Q-mode PCA scores (Figure 10(a)). On the basis of the SHAP analysis (Figure 11(a)), PC6, PC5, and PC4 are considered the most influential factors, contrasting with PC1 and PC2, which best explain the overall variance of the documents, mainly reflecting genre. This finding indicates that the features distinguishing general stylistic differences and those identifying specific authorship exist in different dimensions. To interpret these abstract components in terms of stylistic features, one can examine the word groups that define them through their Q-mode PCA loadings (Table 3). The key insight is that these components serve as axes that

⁴⁴ Coutts, “The Relationship of Ephesians and Colossians,” pp. 201–207.

⁴⁵ Grayston and Herdan, “The authorship of the Pastorals in the light of statistical linguistics,” pp. 1–15.

⁴⁶ Mealand, “The extent of the Pauline corpus,” pp. 61–92.

⁴⁷ Savoy, “Authorship of Pauline epistles revisited,” pp. 1089–1097.

demarcate stylistic boundaries between the core Pauline corpus and other distinct subgroups within the New Testament:

- **PC4 (“Hebrews Axis”):** This component is strongly defined by theological terms unique to Hebrews, such as “Μελχισεδέκ” (Melchizedek, G3198) and “τράγος” (goat, G5131). A high score on PC4, which pushes a document toward a Pauline classification in the model, paradoxically indicates the absence of these uniquely Hebrews-related terms.
- **PC5 (“Ephesians/Colossians Axis”):** This component has high negative loadings for words characteristic of Colossians and Philemon, such as “ἀνήκω” (to be fitting, G433) and “Ονήσιμος” (Onesimus, G3682). A high score on PC5, which pushes a document away from a Pauline classification, indicates a higher frequency of these specific words.
- **PC6 (“Pastoral/Johannine Axis”):** This component contrasts vocabulary specific to the small Johannine epistles (e.g., “ἀντίχριστος,” antichrist, G500) with terms found in the Pastorals. A low score on PC6, indicating a strong non-Pauline signal, points toward the vocabulary profile of these other corpora.

In essence, the model defines “Pauline-ness” not only based on the presence of certain words but also, and perhaps more importantly, by the absence of vocabulary that is highly characteristic of other distinct stylistic groups within the New Testament. This “negative definition” is a key insight provided by the SHAP analysis. Further, the individual force plots (Figures 12(a)–(e)) effectively illustrate why debated documents such as Hebrews and the Deutero-Pauline epistles received their specific prediction probabilities. Hebrews, while displaying some Pauline features (red arrows due to high values of PC4 and PC7), was visualized as having overwhelmingly strong non-Pauline traits (blue arrows due to low values of PC6 and PC5) that counteracted them. This result aligns perfectly with the scholarly theory

that Hebrews was written by an author who, although influenced by Pauline theology, received completely different rhetorical training.⁴⁸

The insights from the R-mode analysis also support this interpretation. In the R-mode random forest model, as indicated by its own SHAP analysis (Figure 11(b)), PC2, PC3, and PC6 were identified as important features. When examining the R-mode principal component scores (Table 5), PC2 was seen to exhibit high scores for central terms of Pauline theology, such as *καυχάομαι* (to boast, G2744) and *παρουσία* (coming, advent, G3952), whereas PC3 exhibited high scores for vocabulary of the Johannine epistles, such as *ἀντίχριστος* (antichrist, G500). When combining these results with those of PC6, which was important in both the Q-mode and R-mode analyses, it can be understood that the model learned a complex pattern of using Pauline theological terms frequently, while not using Johannine technical terms or vocabulary specific to certain epistles.

Therefore, the SHAP analysis revealed that the models are not simply a black box but are based on an interpretable logic that evaluates multiple stylistic aspects in a combined manner. It identifies subtle differences in authorship by capturing the overall patterns created by multiple vocabulary groups, not just the presence or absence of specific words. This “transparency of the judgment process” is one of the achievements brought about by stylometry.

4.4. Future directions

While this study offers a new quantitative approach to stylistic analysis of the New Testament, it also serves as a starting point for further exploration. Future research can branch out in several directions.

⁴⁸ Attridge, *The Epistle to the Hebrews*, pp. 4–5.

First, the model can be refined by expanding the features considered. This study used mainly BM25 scores of lemmatized individual words as features. By incorporating n-grams (combinations of consecutive words), part-of-speech sequences, and syntactic features such as sentence length and structure, it would be possible to capture author style in a more layered manner. Integrating these features could improve analytical accuracy for short texts such as Philemon and highlight more subtle stylistic gradations within the Pauline-related epistles. However, adding complex features to a small corpus increases the risk of overfitting. To mitigate this issue, one could use nested cross-validation, regularization (L1/L2 or elastic net), dimensionality constraints via PCA or feature selection, and learning curve diagnostics to calibrate model capacity.

Second, identifying stylistic traditions can be expanded by increasing the scope of comparative targets. The high-precision classification model developed here is not limited to internal comparisons within the New Testament. Applying this model to the Septuagint (LXX) and other Hellenistic Greek writings from the same period (e.g., Philo or Josephus) can help objectively clarify the uniqueness of stylistic traits such as “Pauline-ness” or “Lukan-ness” within the Greek-speaking world of that era.

Third, the qualitative examination of the key principal components identified by SHAP can be used further. The SHAP analysis indicated that PC6, PC5, and PC4 are significant for recognizing Pauline-ness. Future research should extract specific word groups with high loadings on these components and analyze their theological and rhetorical functions in detail using traditional philological methods. Crucially, these lexeme sets can feed back into model refinement by informing targeted feature engineering (e.g., curated dictionaries, component-specific term weights) for a second iteration of analysis, allowing us to test whether authorship signals become sharper or more robust. Finally, the methodological framework can be expanded. In addition to deepening the theological interpretation of

stylistic elements, future studies might apply similar methods to Pauline apocrypha or early translations such as the Vulgate or Peshitta to trace the reception of Pauline style. Further, incorporating advanced natural language-processing models such as semantic vector models (e.g., Word2Vec) or large language models, could capture higher-order lexical and thematic patterns beyond individual word frequencies. These extensions could further clarify the boundaries of Pauline style across linguistic and textual traditions, positioning this work within the evolving field of computational biblical studies.

4.5 Limitations and scope

The corpus is small (27 documents) and uneven in length, which constrains model complexity and statistical power. Vocabulary is lemmatized Koine Greek; thus, results depend on lemmatization accuracy and text-critical choices, which means that different editions or segmentation could shift loadings. PCA is linear and may not capture a nonlinear structure. Similarly, BM25 emphasizes lexical rather than syntactic signals. Genre remains a potential confounding factor even after PCA. LDA suggests that separation is strong but causality cannot be inferred. Ground-truth labels for authorship reflect scholarly consensus rather than certainties. To address these limitations, multiple distance metrics, both Q- and R-mode PCA, cross-validated supervised models, and SHAP were employed for interpretability. Future work will include sensitivity analyses across editions, robustness checks with alternative stylometric baselines (e.g., function word profiles, Burrows's delta), and out-of-sample validation on related corpora.

5. Conclusion

This study applied a systematic, multi-step stylometric approach, including Okapi BM25 word weighting, dual-mode PCA, multiple clustering techniques, supervised machine

learning, discriminant analysis, and SHAP analysis, to the lemmatized vocabulary data of the 27 New Testament documents. These techniques were chosen over alternatives (e.g., function-word-only profiles, topic models, or purely distance-based methods) because they jointly normalize for document length and genre, yield interpretable component-level signals, and are robust in small-corpus settings. The goal was to re-examine the authorship issue, especially regarding the Pauline epistles, with a focus on objectivity and clarity. The presented findings offer strong, reproducible evidence for a distinct stylistic hierarchy within the New Testament, notably highlighting the clear separation of the Pastoral Epistles from the main Pauline corpus.

The analyses converge on three main conclusions. First, the New Testament documents exhibit a clear and robust stylistic structure, with multiple analytical methods consistently revealing a hierarchical organization in which the Pastoral Epistles form a cluster clearly separated from other Pauline-related letters. Second, a supervised learning model trained on the four major epistles classified “Pauline” versus “non-Pauline” with a high accuracy of 96.2% (Table 7) and assigned extremely low probabilities of Pauline authorship to the Pastoral Epistles (Table 8). This finding adds significant quantitative weight to the critical scholarly consensus that regards the Pastorals as non-Pauline. Third, SHAP analysis revealed that the stylistic features defining “Pauline-ness” are subtle, residing in lower-variance components distinct from the main axes of variation that primarily reflect genre.

In summary, stylometry combined with interpretable machine learning complements rather than displaces traditional biblical scholarship. These quantitative results do not represent a definitive verdict regarding authorship but a valuable addition to historical critical and theological inquiry, offering objective data for debates regarding amanuenses and the development of a “Pauline school.” The findings that PCA effectively filters noise to uncover core stylistic features, in combination with SHAP analysis explaining the reasoning of

machine learning models, are significant. Future research should further probe the essence of Pauline style through theological and philological analysis of the specific vocabulary groups that constitute the key principal components identified in this study.

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Tables

Table 1(1). Top 10 Words with the Highest BM25 Scores for Each Document

01 MT			02 MR			03 LU			
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	5007	τάλαντον	5.14	1568	ἐκθαμβέω	4.09	1665	Ἑλισάβετ	4.55
2	2215	ζιζάνιον	4.47	4017	περιβλέπω	3.84	3414	μνᾶ	4.55
3	3677	ὄναρ	4.05	216	ἄλαλος	3.65	1988	ἐπιστάτης	4.2
4	5273	ὑποκριτής	3.6	2284	θαμβέω	3.65	2197	Ζαχαρίας	3.87
5	1742	ἔνδυμα	3.53	2500	Ἰωσῆς	3.65	2625	κατακλίνω	3.69
6	4816	συλλέγω	3.53	2760	κεντυρίων	3.65	4130	πλήθω	3.56
7	3350	μετοικεσία	3.42	2877	κοράσιον	3.64	905	βαλάντιον	3.33
8	3101	μαθητής	3.42	3885	παραλυτικός	3.64	5336	φάτνη	3.33
9	1030	βρυγμός	3.35	1260	διαλογίζομαι	3.44	3916	παραχρήμα	3.33
10	5028	τάφος	3.35	3850	παραβολή	3.42	5057	τελώνης	3.33

04 JOH			05 AC			06 RO			
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	3482	Ναθαναήλ	4.26	4569	Σαῦλος	5.21	1461	ἐγκεντρίζω	5.12
2	2976	Λάζαρος	4.16	5347	Φῆστος	5.06	5427	φρόνημα	4.64
3	3530	Νικόδημος	3.99	4609	Σίλας	4.97	1575	ἐκκλάω	4.24
4	3795	ὄψάριον	3.99	67	Ἀγρίππας	4.87	2631	κατάκριμα	4.24
5	5596	ψωμίον	3.99	367	Ἀνανίας	4.87	4828	συμμαρτυρέω	4.24
6	3136	Μάρθα	3.97	2445	Ἰόππη	4.75	65	ἀγριέλαιος	3.63
7	501	ἀντλέω	3.65	3343	μεταπέμπω	4.62	379	ἀναπολόγητος	3.63
8	2580	Κανᾶ	3.65	4549	Σαούλ	4.62	460	ἀνόμως	3.63
9	2814	κλῆμα	3.65	5344	Φῆλιξ	4.62	463	ἀνοχή	3.63
10	3101	μαθητής	3.45	2883	Κορνήλιος	4.46	663	ἀποτομία	3.63

Table 1(2). Top 10 Words with the Highest BM25 Scores for Each Document.

07 1CO			08 2CO			09 GA			
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	3472	μωρία	4.95	2571	κάλυμα	5.06	28	Ἰαγὰρ	4.78
2	22	ἄγαμος	4.68	1553	ἐκδημέω	4.73	688	Ἀραβία	4.78
3	5517	χοϊκός	4.68	1736	ἐνδημέω	4.73	2454	Ἰουδαϊσμός	4.78
4	1243	διαίρεσις	4.29	2506	καθαίρεσις	4.73	4323	προσανατίθημι	4.78
5	2386	ἴαμα	4.29	2655	καταναρκάω	4.73	424	ἀνέρχομαι	3.95
6	2619	κατακαλύπτω	4.29	4705	σπουδαῖος	4.73	1944	ἐπικατάρατος	3.95
7	4734	Στεφανᾶς	4.29	4729	στενοχωρέω	4.73	3807	παιδαγωγός	3.95
8	5448	φυσιώω	4.25	2794	κίνδυνος	4.68	4199	πορθέω	3.95
9	3348	μετέχω	4.09	2292	θαρρέω	4.37	4614	Σινᾶ	3.95
10	350	ἀνακρίνω	3.98	3540	νόημα	4.37	5605	ὠδίν	3.95

10 EPH			11 PHP			12 COL			
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	1625	ἐκτρέφω	4.73	1891	Ἐπαφρόδιτος	4.98	554	ἀπεκδύομαι	5
2	1775	ἐνοτής	4.73	4866	συναθλέω	4.98	2993	Λαοδίκεια	4.64
3	3180	μεθοδεία	4.73	2209	ζημία	4.11	604	ἀποκαταλλάσσω	4.12
4	4830	συμμέτοχος	4.73	2771	κέρδος	4.11	1889	Ἐπαφρᾶς	4.12
5	4883	συναρμολογέω	4.73	3444	μορφή	4.11	3787	ὀφθαλμοδουλεία	4.12
6	5235	ὑπερβάλλω	4.28	4297	προκοπή	4.11	4891	συνεγείρω	4.12
7	526	ἀπαλλοτριόω	3.9	55	ἀγνώω	4.06	120	ἀθυμέω	4.08
8	3833	πανοπλία	3.9	144	αἴσθησις	4.06	148	αἰσχρολογία	4.08
9	4318	προσαγωγή	3.9	170	ἀκαιρέομαι	4.06	431	ἀνέψιος	4.08
10	5231	ὑπεράνω	3.9	253	ἀλυπότερος	4.06	466	ἀνταναπληρώω	4.08

Table 1(3). Top 10 Words with the Highest BM25 Scores for Each Document.

13 1TH				14 2TH			15 1TI		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	274	ἀμέμπτως	5.03	814	ἀτάκτως	5.27	423	ἀνεπίληπτος	5.4
2	4035	περιλείπω	5.03	1740	ἐνδοξάζω	5.27	1884	ἐπαρκέω	5.4
3	89	ἀδιαλείπτως	4.48	812	ἀτακτέω	4.46	47	ἀγνεία	5
4	3888	παραμυθέομαι	4.15	1730	ἔνδειγμα	4.46	587	ἀπόδεκτος	5
5	4722	στέγω	4.15	2569	καλοποιέω	4.46	594	ἀποδοχή	5
6	362	ἀναμένω	4.13	4020	περιεργάζομαι	4.46	1783	ἔντευξις	5
7	642	ἀπορφανίζω	4.13	4593	σημειόω	4.46	2085	ἑτεροδιδασκαλέω	5
8	813	ἄτακτος	4.13	5099	τίνω	4.46	2887	κόσμιος	5
9	1559	ἐκδιώκω	4.13	5232	ὑπεραυξάνω	4.46	4200	πορισμός	5
10	1837	ἐξηχέομαι	4.13	3401	μιμέομαι	3.74	795	ἀστοχέω	4.12

16 2TI				17 TIT			18 PHM		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	118	ἀθλέω	5.12	4998	σώφρων	4.67	661	ἀποτίνω	4.74
2	3683	Ὀνησίφορος	5.12	141	αἰρετικός	4.55	682	Ἀπφία	4.74
3	4777	συγκακοπαθέω	5.12	176	ἀκατάγνωστος	4.55	890	ἄχρηστος	4.74
4	72	ἀγωγή	4.24	734	Ἄρτεμάς	4.55	1595	ἐκούσιον	4.74
5	171	ἀκαίρως	4.24	843	αὐτοκατάκριτος	4.55	3685	ὀνίνημι	4.74
6	193	ἀκράτης	4.24	893	ἀψευδής	4.55	4359	προσοφείλω	4.74
7	329	ἀναζωπυρέω	4.24	947	βδελυκτός	4.55	5371	Φιλήμων	4.74
8	359	ἀνάλυσις	4.24	1468	ἐγκρατής	4.55	751	Ἄρχιππος	3.91
9	366	ἀνανήφω	4.24	1612	ἐκστρέφω	4.55	1677	ἐλλογέω	3.91
10	404	ἀναψύχω	4.24	1930	ἐπιδιορθόω	4.55	1889	Ἐπαφρᾶς	3.91

Table 1(4). Top 10 Words with the Highest BM25 Scores for Each Document.

19 HEB				20 JAS			21 IPE		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	3198	Μελχισεδέκ	5.62	182	ἀκατάστατος	4.94	2555	κακοποιός	5.37
2	5131	τράγος	5.22	616	ἀποκυέω	4.94	81	ἀδελφότης	4.96
3	1181	δεκάτη	4.98	1374	δίψυχος	4.94	313	ἀναγεννάω	4.96
4	1336	διηνεκές	4.98	1503	εἶκω	4.94	2029	ἐποπτεύω	4.96
5	3728	ὄρκωμοσία	4.98	3329	μετάγω	4.94	2406	ιεράτευμα	4.96
6	4007	πέρ	4.98	4089	πικρός	4.94	204	ἀκρογωνιαῖος	4.09
7	2663	κατάπαυσις	4.64	5394	φλογίζω	4.94	427	ἄνευ	4.09
8	2100	εὐαρεστέω	4.63	5468	χαλιναγωγέω	4.94	438	ἄνθος	4.09
9	2420	ἱερωσύνη	4.63	202	ἀκροατής	4.61	2272	ἠσύχιος	4.09
10	3331	μετάθεσις	4.63	1150	δαμάζω	4.42	2635	καταλαλέω	4.09

22 2PE				23 1JO			24 2JO		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	668	ἀποφεύγω	5.53	5545	χρίσμα	5.25	2959	Κυρία	5.5
2	1811	ἐξακολουθέω	5.53	31	ἀγγελία	4.81	5489	χάρτης	4.79
3	113	ἄθεσμος	5.16	2434	ἰλασμός	4.81	500	ἀντίχριστος	3.96
4	180	ἀκατάπαυστος	5.16	500	ἀντίχριστος	4.55	4108	πλάνος	3.43
5	793	ἀστήρικτος	5.16	5040	τεκνίον	4.17	3188	μέλαν	3.41
6	1007	Βοσόρ	5.16	443	ἀνθρωποκτόνος	3.97	618	ἀπολαμβάνω	2.39
7	1597	ἔκπαλαι	5.16	2607	καταγινώσκω	3.97	4134	πλήρης	2.39
8	1862	ἐπάγγελμα	5.16	4969	σφάζω	3.97	2841	κοινωνέω	2.16
9	2741	καυσόω	5.16	3529	νίκη	3.84	3029	λίαν	2.16
10	4577	σειρά	5.16	4653	σκοτία	3.61	4254	προάγω	2.16

Table 1(5). Top 10 Words with the Highest BM25 Scores for Each Document.

25 3JO				26 JUDE			27 RE		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	1926	ἐπιδέχομαι	5.51	3921	παρεισδύνω	5.4	1404	δράκων	5.57
2	1361	Διοτρεφής	4.81	592	ἀποδιορίζω	4.66	5357	φιάλη	5.51
3	5383	φιλοπρωτεύω	4.81	679	ἀπταίστος	4.66	3359	μέτωπον	5.14
4	5396	φλυαρέω	4.81	764	ἀσεβέω	4.66	721	ἀρνίον	4.97
5	1216	Δημήτριος	3.97	1113	γογγυστής	4.66	929	βασανισμός	4.81
6	1482	ἐθνικός	3.97	1164	δειγμα	4.66	2462	ἵππος	4.72
7	2137	εὐοδόω	3.91	1608	ἐκπορνεύω	4.66	1039	βύσσινος	4.58
8	3188	μέλαν	3.42	1864	ἐπαγωνίζομαι	4.66	3769	οὐρά	4.58
9	3401	μιμέομαι	3.42	1890	ἐπαφρίζω	4.66	4072	πέτομαι	4.58
10	5274	ὑπολαμβάνω	3.42	2879	Κορέ	4.66	2586	καπνός	4.55

Table 2. Eigenvalues, Explained Variance, and Principal Component Scores for Q-mode PCA.

Metric / Document	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9	PC10
Eigenvalue	884	667	390	354	308	298	241	237	226	213
Explained Variance	0.16	0.12	0.070	0.064	0.056	0.054	0.043	0.043	0.041	0.039
Cumulative Variance	0.16	0.28	0.35	0.414	0.47	0.523	0.567	0.61	0.65	0.689
Principal Component Scores										
01 MT	39.1	53.1	51.7	1.13	8.33	-10.1	-11.0	-49.3	3.99	12.
02 MR	28.2	37.6	45.8	-1.98	6.67	-18.8	6.36	46.3	-1.36	-35.3
03 LU	63.5	74.2	-67.8	-11.2	-2.20	0.32	-0.466	2.52	0.54	-1.81
04 JOH	7.74	11.3	15.4	-3.82	-7.20	0.78	8.96	33.9	-10.8	59.7
05 AC	114.2	-82.3	1.07	-5.13	-1.28	-1.78	-1.20	-1.85	0.44	-1.08
06 RO	-6.94	-3.94	-4.2	18.8	56.2	31.3	-42.1	9.30	-20.9	-0.67
07 1CO	-3.29	0.06	1.05	5.19	26.8	27.5	62.9	-13.7	-22.1	-6.35
08 2CO	-9.72	-4.36	-2.42	3.49	26.8	11.4	8.85	5.92	67.7	5.56
09 GA	-10.2	-4.8	-1.87	-2.6	7.04	0.80	1.44	0.43	-0.52	3.06
10 EPH	-12.9	-4.84	-3.41	-3.39	2.02	-0.34	-1.54	-0.91	-0.97	-4.19
11 PHP	-13.8	-6.03	-3.76	-4.19	3.34	-3.32	1.52	-0.91	4.69	0.44
12 COL	-14.3	-5.68	-2.34	-4.55	-0.16	-2.92	0.72	-1.27	1.4	-3.54
13 1TH	-13.1	-5.61	-2.1	-5.21	0.44	-3.33	1.01	-1.21	1.91	0.14
14 2TH	-14.5	-5.83	-2.49	-5.76	-3.02	-5.54	0.15	-1.78	0.69	-0.91
15 1TI	-13.8	-6.42	-5.66	-5.47	-4.3	-9.81	-1.8	-6.31	-7.68	-14.7
16 2TI	-14.	-7.55	-4.55	-4.99	-2.67	-9.2	-4.2	-2.16	-3.94	-6.54
17 TIT	-16.3	-7.24	-3.98	-8.55	-6.16	-9.62	-2.58	-3.82	-4.11	-3.29
18 PHM	-16.4	-6.78	-2.76	-8.55	-5.15	-8.02	-1.61	-1.90	0.09	-1.2
19 HEB	1.44	0.02	-9.33	89.5	-19.6	-15.2	3.56	-0.23	1.17	-0.06
20 JAS	-9.54	-1.82	-0.94	-3.29	-3.53	-0.46	-4.24	-3.06	-8.52	8.65
21 1PE	-11.9	-5.01	-3.22	-1.12	1.85	-3.82	-3.38	-4.46	-1.39	-0.59
22 2PE	-14.4	-5.59	-3.17	-6.25	-7.35	-8.12	-3.71	-2.38	-2.58	-0.39
23 1JO	-13.6	-4.34	-0.79	-6.29	-5.81	-5.52	-1.37	0.44	-0.62	3.13
24 2JO	-16.3	-6.05	-2.04	-8.76	-6.7	-7.82	-1.97	-1.26	-0.552	-0.10
25 3JO	-16.4	-6.49	-2.41	-9.15	-6.66	-8.04	-1.92	-1.77	-0.466	-0.34
26 JUDE	-15.4	-5.52	-2.05	-7.15	-8.13	-7.36	-2.76	-2.33	-1.44	-0.94
27 RE	2.49	9.9	16.3	-0.72	-49.5	67.0	-9.60	1.88	5.39	-10.7

Table 3(1). Top 10 Words with the Highest Absolute Loadings for Each Q-mode Principal Component.

PC1			PC2			PC3			
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Loading	Strong Number	Word	Loading	Strong Number	Word	Loading
1	2956	Κυρηναῖος	0.95	3994	πενθερά	0.8	1205	δεῦτε	0.77
2	645	ἀποσπάω	0.95	5057	τελώνης	0.8	5614	ώσαννά	0.75
3	4505	ρύμη	0.95	954	Βεελζεβούλ	0.8	3798	ὄψιος	0.75
4	1543	ἐκατοντάρχης	0.94	4615	σίναπι	0.79	2176	εὐώνυμος	0.73
5	1654	ἐλημοσύνη	0.94	2337	θηλάζω	0.79	2293	θαρσέω	0.73
6	2868	κονιορτός	0.93	4260	προβαίνω	0.79	2515	καθέδρα	0.73
7	1733	ἔνδεκα	0.93	4411	πρωτοκλισία	0.79	1310	διαφημίζω	0.73
8	1982	ἐπισκιάζω	0.93	4082	πήρα	0.78	3878	παρακούω	0.73
9	2350	θορυβέω	0.93	3014	λέπρα	0.78	647	ἀποστάσιον	0.73
10	3729	ὀρμάω	0.93	4410	πρωτοκαθεδρία	0.78	3736	ὀρύσσω	0.73

PC4			PC5			PC6			
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Loading	Strong Number	Word	Loading	Strong Number	Word	Loading
1	3331	μετάθεσις	0.97	2349	θνητός	0.75	3691	ὄξύς	0.89
2	5398	φοβερός	0.97	2644	καταλλάσσω	0.74	12	ἄβυσσος	0.87
3	3405	μισθαποδοσία	0.97	3863	παραζηλόω	0.73	2788	κιθάρα	0.85
4	2100	εὐαρεστέω	0.97	1293	διαστολή	0.72	3435	μολύνω	0.84
5	2420	ιερωσύνη	0.97	3800	ὀψώνιον	0.72	4537	σαλπίζω	0.82
6	1183	δεκατόω	0.97	899	βάθος	0.7	5505	χιλιάς	0.82
7	2558	κακουχέω	0.97	2275	ἥττημα	0.69	4203	πορνεύω	0.81
8	115	ἀθέτησις	0.97	4841	συμπάσχω	0.69	948	βδελύσσω	0.81
9	3311	μερισμός	0.97	2907	κρέας	0.69	5005	ταλαίπωρος	0.81
10	4532	Σαλήμ	0.97	1825	ἐξεγείρω	0.69	808	ἀσχημοσύνη	0.81

Table 3(2). Top 10 Words with the Highest Absolute Loadings for Each Q-mode Principal Component.

PC7				PC8			PC9		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Loading	Strong Number	Word	Loading	Strong Number	Word	Loading
1	3472	μωρία	0.83	5145	τριακόσιοι	0.77	550	ἀπειπόμην	0.92
2	1355	διόπερ	0.83	4462	ῥαββονί	0.77	3835	πανοῦργος	0.92
3	2058	ἐρμηνεία	0.83	4101	πιστικός	0.77	532	ἀπαρασκευάστος	0.92
4	3981	πειθός	0.83	3487	νάρδος	0.77	100	ἀδρότης	0.92
5	5424	φρήν	0.83	2415	Ἱεροσολυμίτης	0.77	3912	παραφρονέω	0.92
6	1467	ἐγκρατεύομαι	0.83	174	ἀκάνθινος	0.77	3910	παραντικά	0.92
7	2863	κομάω	0.83	237	ἀλλαχόθεν	0.77	610	ἀπόκριμα	0.92
8	3134	μαράν ἀθά	0.83	1780	ἐνταφιασμός	0.77	3993	πένης	0.92
9	3048	λογία	0.83	4429	πτύω	0.76	1395	δότης	0.92
10	3060	λοιδορος	0.83	4319	προσαιτέω	0.74	1481	ἐθνάρχης	0.92

PC10			
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Loading
1	5176	τρώγω	0.85
2	2608	κατάγνυμι	0.84
3	5596	ψωμίον	0.83
4	3795	ὄψάριον	0.83
5	3530	Νικόδημος	0.83
6	3678	ὄνάριον	0.83
7	502	ἄντλημα	0.83
8	3605	ὄζω	0.83
9	3995	πενθερός	0.83
10	4019	περιδέω	0.83

Table 4. Eigenvalues and Principal Component Loadings for R-mode PCA

Metric / Document	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9	PC10
Eigenvalue	2.14	1.59	1.25	1.15	1.14	1.11	1.09	1.03	1.03	1.01
Explained Variance	0.079	0.059	0.046	0.043	0.042	0.041	0.040	0.038	0.038	0.038
Cumulative Variance	0.079	0.14	0.18	0.23	0.27	0.31	0.35	0.39	0.43	0.46
Principal Component Loadings										
01 MT	0.745	0.148	0.0433	-0.013	0.076	-0.121	0.00153	-0.141	-0.100	-0.0974
02 MR	0.712	0.152	0.0475	-0.0679	0.0941	-0.127	0.0133	-0.112	-0.146	-0.117
03 LU	0.658	0.0559	0.00388	-0.0679	0.0333	-0.105	0.0375	-0.0773	-0.0881	-0.0656
04 JOH	0.538	0.214	0.147	0.0277	-0.0215	0.0254	-0.0304	0.219	-0.00871	0.138
05 AC	0.208	-0.197	-0.196	-0.288	-0.226	0.097	0.195	0.47	0.0243	0.0221
06 RO	-0.170	0.448	-0.0906	0.0959	-0.151	-0.160	-0.215	0.0722	-0.193	-0.0336
07 ICO	-0.001	0.430	-0.104	0.0538	-0.0771	-0.258	-0.0653	0.0626	0.158	-0.0493
08 2CO	-0.146	0.365	-0.125	-0.0568	-0.289	-0.0496	-0.0316	-0.165	-0.116	-0.0606
09 GA	-0.0366	0.356	-0.104	0.076	-0.175	-0.135	-0.143	0.548	-0.0499	-0.0911
10 EPH	-0.135	0.371	-0.156	-0.0306	0.473	0.0465	-0.0609	0.00618	0.212	-0.0139
11 PHP	-0.137	0.315	-0.0435	-0.0873	-0.144	0.0168	0.0256	-0.0993	-0.136	0.150
12 COL	-0.142	0.335	-0.192	-0.196	0.572	0.177	-0.103	0.0578	0.0271	-0.0437
13 1TH	-0.0758	0.392	-0.0654	-0.028	-0.133	-0.0194	0.480	-0.115	0.160	-0.0654
14 2TH	-0.0633	0.350	0.0058	-0.0568	-0.155	0.00391	0.531	-0.168	0.217	0.0164
15 1TI	-0.171	0.029	0.517	-0.153	0.0577	-0.38	0.0499	-0.0333	0.131	0.0532
16 2TI	-0.177	0.0066	0.347	-0.220	0.136	-0.232	0.0653	0.0542	-0.188	0.0404
17 TIT	-0.157	0.0324	0.523	-0.107	0.148	-0.311	-0.0158	0.117	0.0944	-0.0246
18 PHM	-0.0869	0.174	-0.0419	-0.361	0.279	0.175	-0.0323	0.0174	-0.395	0.0145
19 HEB	-0.0415	0.0712	0.0563	0.219	0.0147	0.123	0.162	-0.161	-0.397	0.581
20 JAS	0.0237	0.0936	0.0685	0.370	-0.107	-0.0381	-0.377	-0.0188	0.111	-0.0269
21 IPE	-0.107	0.151	0.0676	0.172	-0.111	-0.078	-0.272	-0.286	-0.185	0.0169
22 2PE	-0.106	0.0195	0.188	0.426	0.115	0.147	0.226	0.195	-0.200	-0.446
23 IJO	0.121	0.275	0.358	0.0567	-0.0704	0.339	-0.0112	0.314	0.0843	0.395
24 2JO	0.0325	0.150	0.361	-0.208	-0.188	0.473	-0.183	-0.0372	0.0354	-0.0882
25 3JO	-0.00228	0.109	0.248	-0.232	-0.211	0.400	-0.153	-0.231	0.111	-0.346
26 JUDE	-0.0247	0.0626	0.197	0.440	0.185	0.173	0.289	0.0609	-0.212	-0.214
27 RE	0.238	0.0593	0.0123	0.292	0.201	0.131	-0.0667	-0.0983	0.495	0.220

Table 5(1). Top 10 Words with the Highest Absolute Scores for Each R-mode Principal Component.

PC1				PC2			PC3		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	3101	μαθητής	8.81	1535	είτε	7.41	500	άντιχριστος	11.79
2	3793	ὄχλος	8.03	2744	καυχάομαι	5.79	2959	Κυρία	10.18
3	1056	Γαλιλαία	7.38	1753	ἐνέργεια	5.35	3188	μέλαν	9.04
4	749	ἀρχιερέυς	7.02	4904	συνεργός	5.33	5489	χάρτης	8.84
5	2491	Ἰωάννης	6.91	3952	παρουσία	5.31	5198	ὑγιαίνω	7.96
6	611	ἀποκρίνομαι	6.81	737	ἄρτι	5.13	4108	πλάνος	7.6
7	5330	Φαρισαῖος	6.78	4152	πνευματικός	5.09	3029	λίαν	6.62
8	190	ἀκολουθέω	6.66	500	άντιχριστος	4.76	5583	ψευστής	6.57
9	906	βάλλω	6.55	3560	νουθετέω	4.68	3141	μαρτυρία	6.3
10	3419	μνημεῖον	6.47	1754	ἐνεργέω	4.65	3670	ὁμολογέω	6.23

PC4				PC5			PC6		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	3188	μέλαν	-7.16	433	ἀνήκω	7.33	500	άντιχριστος	15.19
2	2959	Κυρία	-6.3	3188	μέλαν	-7.17	2959	Κυρία	14.69
3	2217	ζόφος	6.16	1889	Ἐπαφρᾶς	6.98	3188	μέλαν	14.47
4	2226	ζῶον	6	3682	Ὀνήσιμος	6.29	5489	χάρτης	12.85
5	1703	ἐμπαικτής	5.58	751	Ἄρχιππος	6.29	1926	ἐπιδέχομαι	8.96
6	4910	συνευωχέω	5.58	1214	Δημᾶς	5.97	3029	λίαν	7.95
7	5246	ὑπέρογκος	5.58	3065	Λουκᾶς	5.97	1361	Διοτρεφής	7.86
8	1889	Ἐπαφρᾶς	-5.5	3787	ὀφθαλμοδουλεία	5.96	5396	φλυαρέω	7.86
9	5489	χάρτης	-5.5	4891	συνεγείρω	5.96	5383	φιλοπρωτεύω	7.86
10	2173	εὐχρηστος	-5.48	604	ἀποκαταλλάσσω	5.96	4108	πλάνος	7.76

Table 5(2). Top 10 Words with the Highest Absolute Scores for Each R-mode Principal Component.

PC7				PC8			PC9		
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	2331	Θεσσαλονικεύς	7.36	5040	τεκνίον	6.68	5218	ύπακοή	-5.79
2	2720	κατευθύνω	7.03	2607	καταγινώσκω	6.46	2173	εύχρηστος	-5.75
3	1740	ένδοξάζω	6.98	3401	μιμέομαι	-5.5	661	ἀποτίνω	-5.64
4	814	ἀτάκτως	6.98	1926	ἐπιδέχομαι	-5.46	682	Ἀπφία	-5.64
5	3449	μόγθος	6.89	921	Βαρνάβας	5.09	890	ἄχρηστος	-5.64
6	1912	ἐπιβαρέω	6.89	15	ἀγαθοποιέω	-4.92	1595	ἐκούσιον	-5.64
7	1349	δίκη	6.43	5545	χρίσμα	4.87	4359	προσοφείλω	-5.64
8	3639	ὄλεθρος	6.15	5383	φιλοπρωτεύω	-4.8	3685	ὀνίνημι	-5.64
9	4593	σημειόω	5.89	1361	Διοτρεφής	-4.8	5371	Φιλήμων	-5.64
10	2569	καλοποιέω	5.89	5396	φλυαρέω	-4.8	1677	ἐλλογέω	-5.42

PC10			
Rank	Strong Number	Word	Score
1	1926	ἐπιδέχομαι	-7.99
2	1361	Διοτρεφής	-6.99
3	5396	φλυαρέω	-6.99
4	5383	φιλοπρωτεύω	-6.99
5	3188	μέλαν	-6.92
6	5545	χρίσμα	6.36
7	1482	ἐθνικός	-6.12
8	4969	σφάζω	6.02
9	2137	εὐοδόω	-5.91
10	228	ἀληθινός	5.89

Table 6(a). k-means Clustering Results for Q-mode PCA Scores.

	k=3	k=4	k=5	k=6	k=7	k=8
01 MT	1	1	1	0	2	5
02 MR	1	0	0	3	4	6
03 LU	2	2	0	4	6	1
04 JOH	1	0	0	1	1	0
05 AC	1	3	3	5	3	4
06 RO	1	0	0	1	1	7
07 1CO	1	0	4	1	0	0
08 2CO	1	0	0	1	1	0
09 GA	1	0	0	1	1	0
10 EPH	1	0	0	1	1	0
11 PHP	1	0	0	1	1	0
12 COL	1	0	0	1	1	0
13 1TH	1	0	0	1	1	0
14 2TH	1	0	0	1	1	0
15 1TI	1	0	0	1	1	0
16 2TI	1	0	0	1	1	0
17 TIT	1	0	0	1	1	0
18 PHM	1	0	0	1	1	0
19 HEB	0	0	2	1	1	2
20 JAS	1	0	0	1	1	0
21 1PE	1	0	0	1	1	0
22 2PE	1	0	0	1	1	0
23 1JO	1	0	0	1	1	0
24 2JO	1	0	0	1	1	0
25 3JO	1	0	0	1	1	0
26 JUDE	1	0	0	1	1	0
27 RE	1	0	0	2	5	3

Table 6(b). k-means Clustering Results for R-mode PCA Loadings.

	k=3	k=4	k=5	k=6	k=7	k=8
01 MT	0	1	1	1	2	1
02 MR	0	1	1	1	2	1
03 LU	0	1	1	1	2	1
04 JOH	0	1	1	1	2	1
05 AC	0	1	1	1	4	1
06 RO	1	0	0	0	0	2
07 1CO	1	0	0	0	0	2
08 2CO	1	0	0	0	0	2
09 GA	1	0	1	0	0	2
10 EPH	1	2	2	5	5	5
11 PHP	1	0	0	0	0	2
12 COL	1	2	2	5	5	5
13 1TH	1	0	0	0	0	0
14 2TH	1	0	0	0	0	0
15 1TI	0	1	3	3	1	4
16 2TI	0	1	3	3	1	4
17 TIT	0	1	3	3	1	4
18 PHM	1	2	2	5	5	5
19 HEB	0	1	1	3	2	6
20 JAS	0	1	1	0	0	2

21 1PE	1	1	0	0	0	2
22 2PE	0	1	4	4	6	7
23 1JO	0	1	1	2	2	6
24 2JO	2	3	1	2	3	3
25 3JO	2	3	0	2	3	3
26 JUDE	0	1	4	4	6	7
27 RE	0	1	1	1	2	1

Table 7. Performance of Supervised Learning Models for Authorship Attribution.

Dataset	Algorithm	Accuracy (Mean)	Accuracy (Std Dev)	TN	FP	FN	TP
BM25_Raw	Logistic_Regression	0.851	0.0103	23	0	4	0
BM25_Raw	Random_Forest	0.851	0.0103	23	0	4	0
PCA_Scores_Q-mode	Logistic_Regression	0.851	0.0103	23	0	4	0
PCA_Scores_Q-mode	Random_Forest	0.962	0.0659	23	0	1	3
PCA_Loadings_R-mode	Logistic_Regression	0.959	0.0658	23	0	1	3
PCA_Loadings_R-mode	Random_Forest	0.922	0.0747	23	0	1	3

This table presents the performance of Logistic Regression and Random Forest models across three different datasets. Performance is measured by mean accuracy and standard deviation from 30 repetitions of 4-fold stratified cross-validation, and a confusion matrix (TN, FP, FN, TP) from a single stratified k-fold validation.

Table 8. Predicted Probabilities of Being a Core Pauline Epistle.

	Prob_Logistic _Regression_ BM25_Raw	Prob_Rando m_Forest_B M25_Raw	Prob_Logistic _Regression_ PCA_Scores_ Q-mode	Prob_Rando m_Forest_PC A_Scores_Q- mode	Prob_Logistic_ Regression_P CA_Loadings _R-mode	Prob_Rando m_Forest_PC A_Loadings_ R-mode
01 MT	0.000254	0.07	0.0355	0.12	0.0219	0.03
02 MR	0.000254	0.06	0.0332	0.1	0.0244	0.01
03 LU	0.000234	0.1	0.0348	0	0.0165	0.02
04 JOH	0.00037	0.07	0.0615	0.1	0.0406	0.02
05 AC	8.21E-05	0.05	0.0379	0	0.0244	0.06
06 RO	0.999	0.74	0.889	0.88	0.851	0.88
07 1CO	0.998	0.7	0.885	0.8	0.699	0.78
08 2CO	0.998	0.76	0.871	0.83	0.589	0.72
09 GA	0.997	0.68	0.157	0.61	0.875	0.75
10 EPH	0.000532	0.04	0.0985	0	0.0636	0.12
11 PHP	0.000617	0.05	0.117	0.07	0.196	0.03
12 COL	0.000541	0.02	0.0842	0	0.0383	0.04
13 1TH	0.000715	0.08	0.0878	0.01	0.135	0.12
14 2TH	0.000563	0.02	0.0605	0	0.0555	0.06
15 1TI	0.000394	0.06	0.035	0	0.0123	0.05
16 2TI	0.000393	0.01	0.0434	0	0.0127	0.03
17 TIT	0.000254	0.03	0.0341	0	0.0135	0.03
18 PHM	0.000383	0	0.0439	0	0.0235	0.01
19 HEB	0.000316	0.07	0.0318	0.13	0.00414	0.01
20 JAS	0.000433	0.05	0.0548	0.02	0.121	0.04
21 1PE	0.000505	0.09	0.0825	0.02	0.116	0.06
22 2PE	0.000325	0.02	0.0338	0	0.0148	0.01
23 1JO	0.000445	0	0.0465	0.05	0.0143	0.02
24 2JO	0.000276	0	0.0387	0	0.0115	0.03
25 3JO	0.00024	0.01	0.0384	0	0.0163	0.02
26 JUDE	0.000232	0.01	0.0342	0	0.00497	0
27 RE	0.000264	0.06	0.0293	0.18	0.00287	0

Table 9. Feature Importance for Random Forest Models.

Feature	Importance_Random_Forest _PCA_Scores_Q-mode	Importance_Random_Forest _PCA_Loadings_R-mode
PC1	0.0231	0.0266
PC2	0.0335	0.269
PC3	0.0162	0.153
PC4	0.107	0.0616
PC5	0.278	0.103
PC6	0.250	0.124
PC7	0.128	0.0622
PC8	0.0763	0.0953
PC9	0.0697	0.0456
PC10	0.018	0.0599

Table 10. Explained Variance for Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA).

Discriminant	Explained_Var _BM25_Raw	Cumulative_Var _BM25_Raw	Explained_Var_ Q-mode_Scores	Cumulative_Var_ Q-mode_Scores	Explained_Var_ R-mode_Loadings	Cumulative_Var_ R-mode_Loadings
LD1	1.000	1.000	0.718	0.718	0.596	0.596
LD2	1.88E-33	1.000	0.275	0.993	0.29	0.886
LD3	4.48E-34	1.000	0.00663	1.000	0.078	0.964
LD4	3.03E-35	1.000	0.000136	1.000	0.025	0.989
LD5	1.34E-35	1.000	5.8E-06	1.000	0.0106	1.000

Table 11. Discriminant Scores for Each Document from Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA).

DataSource		BM25_Raw	Q-mode_Scores					R-mode_Loadings				
Document	LD_Component Group	LD1	LD1	LD2	LD3	LD4	LD5	LD1	LD2	LD3	LD4	LD5
01 MT	Gospels_Acts	-2.5E+16	16.5	-22.1	0.33	0.0997	-0.923	5.06	-7.86	-0.0279	0.861	-0.0237
02 MR	Gospels_Acts	-2.5E+16	16.5	-22.6	0.335	-1.36	0.608	4.42	-7.97	-0.278	0.896	-0.113
03 LU	Gospels_Acts	-2.5E+16	16.5	-22.3	0.341	-0.623	-0.375	4.19	-8.06	0.366	0.77	-0.127
04 JOH	Gospels_Acts	-2.5E+16	16.0	-21.7	-0.006	2.32	1.28	4.14	-5.14	-0.17	-0.174	-0.0819
05 AC	Gospels_Acts	-2.5E+16	16.5	-22.3	0.306	-0.597	-0.586	3.67	-6.72	0.28	0.225	-0.146
06 RO	CorePauline	-2.5E+16	2.79	5.35	-5.44	-0.477	-2.06	3.17	3.03	-3	-2.38	-0.631
07 ICO	CorePauline	-2.5E+16	2.65	5.04	-5.46	-0.659	-0.887	1.66	1.33	-4	-0.423	-0.673
08 2CO	CorePauline	-2.5E+16	2.44	4.78	-5.40	1.09	2.73	3.8	2.79	-1.42	-1.53	-0.309
09 GA	CorePauline	-2.5E+16	2.22	4.34	-0.664	-0.0517	0.149	4.42	-0.0679	-4.81	-1.93	-0.169
10 EPH	DeuteroPauline	-2.5E+16	-0.08	6.85	0.063	-0.219	-0.0195	-0.153	5.48	-1.5	2.83	-1.03
11 PHP	Others	-2.5E+16	0.54	6.27	-0.17	-0.114	0.417	1.38	2.51	0.362	-1.1	-1.01
12 COL	DeuteroPauline	-2.5E+16	-0.20	7.00	0.295	-0.19	0.19	0.743	5.05	-0.925	3.2	-1.12
13 1TH	Others	-2.5E+16	1.14	5.98	0.227	-0.0903	0.284	1.63	3.14	-1.01	1.1	-0.662
14 2TH	DeuteroPauline	-2.5E+16	-0.05	6.51	0.753	-0.135	0.26	0.0131	2.84	-0.0632	1.27	-0.666
15 1TI	Pastoral	-2.5E+16	-3.37	9.14	1.53	-0.906	-0.294	-16.6	-2.54	-0.91	-0.203	0.000825
16 2TI	Pastoral	-2.5E+16	-1.98	7.33	1.22	-0.541	0.0127	-12.3	-2.63	0.194	-0.39	-0.592
17 TIT	Pastoral	-2.5E+16	0.16	8.09	1.60	-0.373	0.0886	-15.5	-2.27	-1.44	-0.0327	0.388
18 PHM	Others	-2.5E+16	1.15	7.55	1.25	-0.181	0.293	-0.35	0.555	1.14	0.874	-1.09
19 HEB	Hebrews	6.61E+17	-90.9	-19.7	-0.275	0.0145	0.000398	0.309	1.34	6.82	-2.1	-2.33
20 JAS	Others	-2.5E+16	1.04	2.77	0.777	0.226	-0.222	1.74	1.46	-0.0616	-1.76	1.18
21 1PE	Others	-2.5E+16	-2.38	5.52	0.266	-0.231	-5.3E-05	-0.317	1.94	1.16	-2.16	0.184
22 2PE	Others	-2.5E+16	-1.00	6.19	1.52	-0.149	0.132	0.478	2.16	0.701	-0.123	1.93
23 1JO	Others	-2.5E+16	0.977	4.78	1.06	0.0807	0.281	0.579	1.51	1.93	-0.694	0.229
24 2JO	Others	-2.5E+16	1.36	7.06	1.40	-0.0986	0.282	0.716	1.92	1.27	0.0739	2.58
25 3JO	Others	-2.5E+16	1.50	7.38	1.42	-0.121	0.283	1.15	2.2	0.307	0.849	3.18
26 JUDE	Others	-2.5E+16	-0.37	6.72	1.52	-0.0949	0.17	0.538	2.38	2.62	0.111	0.946
27 RE	Others	-2.5E+16	0.34	6.16	1.19	3.38	-2.09	1.41	1.64	2.45	1.94	0.182

Table 12(a). Loadings of Principal Components on Discriminant Functions (Q-mode PCA Scores).

Principal Component	LD1	LD2	LD3	LD4	LD5
PC1	5.05	-9.28	-0.0271	-0.0943	-0.19
PC2	2.24	-3.97	0.00313	0.0515	-0.044
PC3	3.08	-2.10	0.0376	0.167	-0.0258
PC4	-16.9	-3.62	-0.56	0.0256	-0.0961
PC5	4.61	0.474	-1.57	-0.422	0.0423
PC6	2.48	2.37	-0.916	0.564	-0.462
PC7	-0.483	-0.54	-0.515	-0.0635	0.246
PC8	1.37	-2.26	-0.107	0.0942	0.297
PC9	-0.348	0.285	-0.404	0.256	0.56
PC10	1.56	-2.62	-0.124	0.481	0.237

Table 12(b). Loadings of Principal Components on Discriminant Functions (R-mode PCA Loadings).

Principal Component	LD1	LD2	LD3	LD4	LD5
PC1	2.61	-2.79	0.0359	0.297	0.0739
PC2	1.20	1.26	-0.974	-0.00247	-0.171
PC3	-3.13	-0.30	0.124	-0.169	0.479
PC4	1.22	0.967	0.492	-0.464	0.149
PC5	-1.33	0.401	0.203	0.918	-0.317
PC6	2.33	1.46	1.03	0.349	0.47
PC7	-0.32	-0.128	0.42	0.409	-0.275
PC8	0.242	-0.579	-0.792	-0.167	-0.00536
PC9	-0.618	0.528	-0.481	0.643	0.247
PC10	-0.503	0.000998	1.02	-0.311	-0.697

Figure 1

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

